

Table S1. Functions of the lncRNA hits

Gene name	Molecular mechanisms	Function
NEAT1	<p>RNA-Protein: PSPC1, NONO/p54nrb, SFPQ/PSF, CDC5L, STAT3, ERa, SIN3A, FOXN3, PGK1, ENO1, PGAM, WDR5, NEDD4L, EZH2, BRG1, P300/CBP, DNMT1, CDK19, CyclinL1, SFPQ, TRAF6, SRSF 5, U2AF65</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miRNA - miR-338-3p, 133b, 141-3p, 218-5p, 138-5p, 410-3p, 107, 448, 211, 129-5p, 361, 124, 133a, 34a, 186-5p, let-7 g-5p, 185-5p, 150-5p, 196a-5p, 193a-3p, 486-5p, 205-5p, 195-5p, 34a, 202-3p, 144-3p, 361, 214-3p, 590-3p, 129, 335, 365a-3p, 142-5p, 221-5p, 30a-3p, 1224-5p, 1294, 506, 335-5p, 500a-3p, 370-3p, 185-5p, 152-3p, 139-5p, 132, 449b-5p, 503, 320a, 22-3p, 296-5p, 139-5p, 485, 124-3p, 448, 204-5p, 495-3p, 200b-3p, 23a-3p, 214, 222, 101-3p, 204, 376b-3p, 101-3p, let-7a, 377-3p, 98-5p, 26a-5p, 1224, 483, 339-5p, 186-5p, 1321, let-7 g, 4500, 382-3p, 101, 302a-3p, 335-5p, 34a-5p, 204-5p, 98-5p, 24-3p, 148b-3p, 3619-5p, 204, 491, 592, 129-5p, 106b-5p, 339-5p</p> <p>mRNA - TNFRSF1B, ELF3</p> <p>RNA-DNA: P21 , Myog, Myh4, Tnni2, LATS2, β-catenin, Smad7</p>	<p>NEAT1 is a well-known component of nuclear paraspeckles, which are dynamic nuclear bodies involved in various aspects of gene regulation, including RNA processing, retention, and sequestration. NEAT1 provides a scaffold for paraspeckle assembly and maintenance. NEAT1 has been suggested to influence gene expression by modulating transcriptional activity. It interacts with transcription factors and epigenetic modifiers, contributing to the regulation of target gene expression. Protein- NEAT1 complexes formation can be divided into three types: a guide, decoy, and scaffold. Complexes regulate transcription activation or repression, Wnt-β-catenin pathway, ubiquitination, miRNA processing, expression level and mRNA splicing. Also, NEAT1 has been implicated in cellular stress responses, such as heat shock and DNA damage. It can dynamically reorganize within the nucleus in response to stress and might takes part in coordinating stress-related gene expression changes. Long noncoding RNA NEAT1 has been associated with various types of cancer such as acute myeloid leukemia, breast cancer, cervical cancer, cholangiocarcinoma, colorectal cancer, endometrial cancer, esophageal carcinoma, gallbladder cancer, gastric cancer, glioblastoma, glioma, hepatocellular carcinoma, Hodgkin's lymphoma , laryngeal carcinoma, melanoma, multiple myeloma, nasopharyngeal carcinoma, lung cancer, osteosarcoma, ovarian cancer, pancreatic carcinoma, prostate cancer, retinoblastoma, retinoblastoma, thyroid cancer, tongue carcinoma. NEAT1 can bind to various miRNAs to regulate the activation of oncogenic proteins. Its expression levels can vary in different cancers, and it has been linked to tumor progression, metastasis, and chemoresistance. It should be mentioned that NEAT1 can directly bind and stabilize mRNA to regulate NF-κB signaling pathway (TNFRSF1B mRNA) and promote the proliferation and metastasis of pancreatic cancer (ELF3 mRNA). NEAT1 might affect cancer-related processes by influencing gene expression patterns and cellular responses to stress. Tre role NEAT1 has been investigated in the context of neurological disorders. It is highly expressed in neurons and glial cells, and its dysregulation has been linked to neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease,</p>

		<p>and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. NEAT1 has been observed to have roles in antiviral responses. It can interact with viral RNAs and proteins, influencing host-virus interactions</p>
SNHG12	<p>RNA-Protein: -</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miRNA - miR-129, miR-195, miR-218, miR-125b, miR-101-3p, miR-199a/b-5p, miR-424-5p, miR-195, miR-195-5p, miR-320, miR-320a, miR-181a, miR-150, miR-136-5p, miR-326, miR-199b, miR-525-5p, miR-129-5p, miR-138</p> <p>RNA-DNA: -</p>	<p>SNHG12 has been reported to be upregulated in several types of cancers, including Ovarian cancer, Prostate cancer, Non-small-cell lung cancer, Cervical cancer, Oral Squamous Cell carcinoma, Glioma, Gastric carcinoma, Hepatocellular carcinoma, Colorectal cancer, and Hepatocellular carcinoma. Its upregulation has been linked to promoting cancer cell proliferation, migration, invasion, and tumor growth. It has been suggested that SNHG12 might act as an oncogenic lncRNA by affecting signaling pathways Slug/ZEB2, Notch2/Notch, Wnt/β-catenin, PI3K/AKT, NF-κB and promoting tumor progression. It was demonstrated that SNHG12 regulates drug resistance in Osteosarcoma, Non-small-cell lung cancer. SNHG12 has been implicated in promoting EMT in cancer cells, thereby contributing to cancer metastasis. SNHG12 can indirectly influence the expression of genes that are regulated by these miRNAs. SNHG12 has been suggested to play a role in regulating the cell cycle. The involvement of SNHG12 has been demonstrated in many mechanisms associated with the pathogenesis of cancer, such as evasion of the immune response and cellular response to DNA damage. Furthermore, SNHG12 participates in the regulation of hypertensive vascular endothelial damage, inflammatory processes of osteoarthritis, various nervous system disorders, ischemic stroke, and the associated process of autophagy.</p>

EPB41L4A-AS1	<p>RNA-Protein: HDAC2, NPM1</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miRNA - miRNA-146a, miR-105-5p</p> <p>RNA-DNA: VDAC1 and VHL</p>	<p>LncRNA EPB41L4A-AS1 regulates glycolysis and glutamine metabolism by modulating the epigenetic regulation of VDAC1 and VHL through HDAC2.</p> <p>lncRNA EPB41L4A-AS1 sponged miR-105-5p to promote GIMAP6 transcription in NSCLC cells. lncRNA EPB41L4A-AS1 was correlated with tumor size and clinical symptoms.</p>
SNHG16	<p>RNA-Protein: EZH2, Caspase3, Caspase9, SPI1</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miRNA - miR-16, miR-205, miR-98-5p, miR-1301, miR-340, miR-96, miR-17-5p, miR-4518, miR-373, miR-628, miR-135a, hsa-miR-17-5p, hsa-miR-93, miR-140-5p, miR-302a-3p, miR-4500, miR-186, miR-196, miR-146a</p> <p>RNA-DNA: p21</p>	<p>SNHG16 has been implicated in several types of cancers, including gastric cancer, colorectal cancer, ovarian cancer, and glioma. Its expression has been reported to be dysregulated in these cancers and it is involved in cancer related processes such as promoting proliferation, activating migration and invasion, inhibiting apoptosis, development of chemoresistance and vasculogenic mimicry. lncRNA SNHG16 is involved in mTOR pathway, PI3K/AKT and NF-κB signaling pathways. SNHG16 can directly inhibit the expression of target gene by sequestration EZH2 to their promoter regions. Additionally, the engagement of SNHG16 in inflammatory processes associated with nerve injury, osteoarthritis, osteoporosis, atherosclerosis, and diabetes has already been established. .</p>
SNHG1	<p>RNA-Protein: DNMT1, p53, EZH2, TCF12</p>	<p>SNHG1 has been implicated in several types of cancers, including colorectal cancer, ovarian cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma, and gastric cancer. Its</p>

	<p>RNA-RNA: miRNA - miR-338, miR-137, miR-18a, miR-145a-5p, miR-577, miR-199a-3p, miR-326, miR-338-3p, miR-181c-5p, miR-181a-5p, miR-424-5p, miR-186-5p, miR-145-5p, miR-382-5p, miR-194-5p, miR-140-5p, miR-196a, miR-153-3p, miR-377-3p, miR-15a-5p, miR-330-5p, miR-497, miR-204, miR-381, miR376, miR-383-5p, miR-18b-5p, miR-326, miR-195-5p, miR-154-5p, miR-194, miR-361-3p, miR-340-5p, miR-573, miR-137-3p, microRNA-9-3p, miR-556-5p, miR-488-5p, miR-195-5p, miR-199a-3p, miR-556-5, miR-101-3p, miR-140, miR-376a, miR-145-5p, miR-193a-5p, miR-15b, miR-377-3p, miR-363-3p, miR140-3p, miR-329-3p, miR-450b-5p, miR-145-5p, miR-221, miR-298, miR-216b-5p, miR-15a,</p>	<p>dysregulation has been associated with cancer progression, metastasis, and drug resistance. SNHG1 is thought to promote oncogenic processes by influencing Wnt/β-catenin, P53 signaling pathways and gene expression patterns. SNHG1 has been reported to take part in promoting. It might affect cancer cell proliferation, migration, invasion, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), and cytoskeletal dynamics. SNHG1 has been proposed to function as an epigenetic regulator by interacting with chromatin-modifying complexes DNMT1, EZH2. It might contribute to gene expression changes by influencing chromatin structure and accessibility. SNHG1 has also been associated with metabolic processes, particularly in the context of cancer metabolism. It could influence metabolic pathways and contribute to the altered energy requirements of cancer cells. In addition to cancer, SNHG1 has been linked to cardiovascular diseases. It has been reported to play roles in endothelial cell function, angiogenesis, and atherosclerosis.</p>
	<p>RNA-DNA: KLF2, CDKN2B,</p>	
<p>SNHG7</p>	<p>RNA-Protein: p15, p16, p22, Bax, p53, β-catenin, DNMT1, SRSF1, TARBP2, METTL3, Tbx5, E2F1, EIF4G2, SP1, EZH2, YY1</p>	<p>SNHG7 can partly promote the development of pancreatic cancer, breast cancer, colon cancer, cervical cancer, liver cancer, thyroid cancer, non-small cell lung cancer, nasopharyngeal carcinoma, lung adenocarcinoma, prostate cancer, ovarian cancer, esophageal cancer, acute myeloid leukemia,</p>

	<p>RNA-RNA: miRNA - miR-34a-5p, miR-193b, miR-5095, miR-186, miR-216b, miR-503, miR-342-3p, miR-449a, miR-34a, miR-485-5p, miR-2682-5p, miR-514-5p, miR-15a, miR-214-5p, miR-29b, miR-485-5p, miR-9, miR-146b-5p, miR-329-3p, miR-6512-3p, miR-122-5p, miR-449a, miR-9-5p, miR-378a-3p, miR-138-5p, miR-17-5p, miR-181a-5p, miR-29b, miR-342-3p, miR-6512-3p, miR-214-5p, miR-425, miR-146b-5p, miR-653-5p, miR-193b, miR-181b-5p, miR-140-5p, miR-134-5p, miRNA-181, miR-2116-5p, miR-186-5p, miR-543, miR-3127-5p, miR-503, miR-625, miR-455-3p, miR-506-3p</p> <p>mRNA - SDAD1</p> <p>RNA-DNA: p53</p>	<p>glioblastoma. SHNHG7 has been reported to promote cancer cell proliferation, migration, and invasion. It might affect these processes by interacting with molecules and signaling pathways involved in cell cycle regulation, EMT, and extracellular matrix remodeling, chemoresistance. It has been shown that SHNHG7 plays a role in Wnt/β-catenin/EMT, Notch-1, PI3K/Akt/mTOR, ERK/MAPK, TGF-β/SMAD4, NF-κB signaling pathways.</p> <p>It was suggested involved in regulation processes of hypoxia/reoxygenation-induced cardiomyocyte damage, spinal cord injury-induced inflammatory response, neurological disease progression - glucose deprivation-induced neuron cell injury, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, atherosclerosis. Additionally, it was shown that METTL3 installed the m6A modification and enhanced the stability of SNHG7 in diabetes.</p>
MIR17HG	<p>RNA-Protein: METTL3</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miRNA- miR-138-5p, miR-17-5p, miR-375, miR-130a-3p, miR-142-3p, miR-155-5p, miR-21, miR-454-3p, miR-18a/19a, miR-142-3p, miR-17, miR-17-92</p> <p>mRNA - CLDN6</p> <p>RNA-DNA: -</p>	<p>MIR17HG exhibits carcinogenically in osteosarcoma, glioma, cervical squamous cell carcinoma, colorectal cancer, gastric cancer, atypical teratoid rhabdoid tumors. MIR17HG is involved in p38/Elk-1, NF-κB/RELA signaling pathway. There is a presumed connection between the lncRNA MIR17HG and the pathogenesis of Parkinson's disease.</p>
SCARNA10	<p>RNA-Protein: p53, ATF3</p> <p>RNA-RNA: -</p>	<p>SCARNA10 exerts a direct activation of transcription through the enhancement of acetylation within the p53 C-terminal domain (CTD), while it leaves p53 phosphorylation at Ser15 unaffected. SCARNA10 introduces a fresh element in the regulation of p53 acetylation-dependent transcriptional function and its role in inhibiting tumor growth.</p> <p>In a TGF-β/SMAD3-dependent manner, SCARNA10 stimulates the</p>

	<p>RNA-DNA: -</p>	<p>expression of ATF3, uncovering a TGF-β/ATF3/lnc-SCARNA10 pathway that contributes to liver fibrosis by stimulating hepatic stellate cells.</p>
CRNDE	<p>RNA-Protein: hnRNPUL2, SRSF6,EZH2, TP53, FOXM1, PAK7, XIAP, DMBT1/C-IAP1, PI3K, TLR3, PRC2, ETS1</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miR-181a-5p, miR-217, miR-186, miR-384, miR-136-5p, miR-384, miR-217, miR-203, miR-136-5p, miR-337-3p, miR-33a-5p, miR-203, miR-641, miR-338-3p, miR-183, miR-4262, miR-136, miR-384, miR-29c-3p, miR-136-5p, miR-101, miR-205, miR-451,miR-181, miR-345-5p, miR-28, miR-337-3p, miR-3163, miR-29a-3p, miR-455-3p, miR-181a-5p, miR-1277,miR-545-5p</p> <p>RNA-DNA: CDKN1A and DUSP5</p>	<p>CRNDE is a lncRNA with a crucial role in cancer development. Its roles in carcinogenesis have been assessed in hematological malignancies such as Acute myeloid leukemia, acute lymphoblastic leukemia and multiple myeloma. Moreover, ovarian cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma, lung cancer, colorectal cancer, nasopharyngeal carcinoma, glioma, glioblastoma, medulloblastoma, oral squamous cell carcinoma, prostate cancer, pancreatic cancer, osteosarcoma, cervical cancer, renal cell carcinoma, melanoma, bladder cancer, papillary thyroid cancer and Breast cancer. CRNDE can act as a regulator of Wnt/β-catenin, PI3K/AKT, NF-κB/AKT and Ras/MAPK signaling pathway. CRNDE interact with different enzymes and transcription factor as well as realize miRNA sponging</p>
LINC00680	<p>RNA-Protein: GATA6, METTL3</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miRNA - miR-423-5p, miR-568, miR-320b, miR-320a, miR-410-3p mRNA - SIRT1</p> <p>RNA-DNA: -</p>	<p>LINC00680 influences cancer development by attracting microRNAs and binding to transcription factors. It also realizes the mechanism of osteoarthritis regulation by interacting with METTL3 methyltransferase.</p>
SHNG25	<p>RNA-Protein: DKC1</p>	<p>SNHG25 is highly expressed in prostate cancer, clear cell renal cell carcinoma, ovarian cancer, endometrial cancer, osteosarcoma, glioma, neuroblastoma and facilitates cancer development through sponging microRNA, protein or RNA binding. SNHG25 involved in regulation of PI3K/AKT, MAPK signaling pathway.</p>
	<p>RNA-RNA: miRNA -miR-579-5p, miR-497-5p RNA - SNORA50C</p> <p>RNA-DNA: -</p>	

SNHG6	<p>RNA-Protein: hnRNPA1, EZH2</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miRNA - miR-26a, miR-26b, miR-214, miR-181a-5p, miR-26a-5p, miR-101-3p, miR-139-5p, let-7c-5p, miR-186-5p, miR-181d-5p, miR-944, miR-490-3p, miR-760, miR-490-3p, miR-1297, miR-125b, miR-181, miR-214, miR-1395p</p> <p>RNA-DNA: P27, JNK, P21</p>	<p>SNHG6 might play a role in facilitating processes like cell migration, invasion, metastasis, cell cycle progression, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), autophagy, and genome-wide hypomethylation. SNHG6 is implicated in activating pathways including the JNK pathway, PI3K/AKT/mTOR pathway, and TGFβ/SMAD pathway. There is a growing body of knowledge highlighting the potential correlation between SNHG6 and vitamin D levels.</p>
LINC00339	<p>RNA-Protein: -</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miR-145, miR-1182, miR-152, miR-377-3p, miR-497-5p, miR-4656, miR-378a-3p, miR-539-5p</p> <p>RNA-DNA: -</p>	<p>LINC00339 is linked to a wide range of diseases, including endometriosis, cardiomyocyte apoptosis, osteoporosis, hepatocellular carcinoma, colorectal cancer, gastric cancer, breast cancer, and prostate cancer. The expression of LINC00339 is notably connected with various clinical characteristics. Additionally, the interrelationships between LINC00339 and patient clinical features, such as prognoses, disease staging, lymphatic metastases, distant metastases, and pathology severity, have been unveiled. Furthermore, LINC00339 significantly fosters the progression of tumors, invasiveness, and tumor growth by orchestrating cellular biological functions.</p> <p>Mechanistically, LINC00339 is reported to function as a competitive endogenous RNA, modulating gene regulation and influencing RNA metabolism. It acts as a sponge for miRNAs, competing with endogenous miRNAs and thereby modulating downstream target genes. Crucial signaling pathways, including the Wnt/β-catenin pathway, MAPK signaling pathways, and RhoA pathway, have also been identified as targets influenced by LINC00339.</p>
LINC00263	<p>RNA-Protein: hnRNPK, OCT4</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miR-147a</p> <p>RNA-DNA: SCD</p>	<p>The LINC00263 RNA, regulated by hnRNPK, assumes a crucial function in cancer aggressiveness. It operates as a miR-147a decoy, consequently leading to the increased expression of CAPN2. LncRNA physically interacted with OCT4 to promote its stabilization via disrupting the ubiquitination. Specifically, it was shown that LINC00263 promotes liver expression of SCD in cis through regional chromosomal DNA-DNA looping interactions in nonalcoholic fatty liver disease.</p>

SNHG30	<p>RNA-Protein: -</p> <p>RNA-RNA: -</p> <p>RNA-DNA: -</p>	Were identified in comprehensive analysis for lung squamous cell carcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma and endocervical adenocarcinomas
LINC00493	<p>RNA-Protein: -</p> <p>RNA-RNA: -</p> <p>RNA-DNA: -</p>	Mechanism of action and functions are described only for translated SMIM26 peptide. For LINC00493, cell type specific influence on the cell viability in cancer cell lines was demonstrated.
SNHG15	<p>RNA-Protein: RABL2A, Slug, EZH2/PRC2, MYC, E2F1</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miRNA - miR-141-3p, miR-153, miR-211-3p, miR-510-5p, miR-486, miR-200a-3p, miR-338-3p, miR-141</p> <p>RNA-DNA: SUZ12, P15 and KLF2</p>	SNHG15 is identified as a key regulator in tumorigenesis and progression of various human cancers, including colorectal cancer, gastric cancer, pancreatic cancer and hepatocellular carcinoma. dysregulation of SNHG15 has been revealed to be dramatically correlated with advanced clinicopathological factors and predicts poor prognosis, suggesting its potential clinical value as a promising biomarker and therapeutic target for cancer patients. SNHG15 has been identified for its fundamental role in regulating proliferation, apoptosis, autophagy, metastasis, immuno-escape, and chemoresistance. SNHG15 act as miRNA sponge, epigenetic regulator and by TF binding. SNHG15 is involved in some signaling pathways essential for cancer, including EMT, WNT/ β -catenin, NF-kb and YAP-Hippo pathways. Moreover, SNHG15 is a critical regulatory factor that aids SARS-CoV-2 entry through RABL2A. The number of studies investigating the functions of SNHG15 in ischemia and hypoxia is increasing.
LINC01420	<p>RNA-Protein: c-MYC</p> <p>RNA-RNA: miRNA - miR-494-3p, miR-149-5p</p> <p>RNA-DNA: -</p>	For the LINC01420 transcript, mechanisms for performing regulatory functions in the cell nucleus and cytoplasm were demonstrated, and the following molecular partners were identified: miR-149-5p, miR-494-3p in the cytoplasm, and c-MYC in the nucleus. MYC-mediated activation of the KRAS proto-oncogene was shown. The role LINC01420 in progression of Gastric Cancer, Nasopharyngeal carcinoma, Pancreatic Cancer, Thyroid cancer.

